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Disability and perceived social exclusion in later working age in Germany – what role does employment play? A counterfactual mediation analysis¹★^{1,★}

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HIGHLIGHTS

- 6.3% of men and 6.6% of women between the ages of 40 and 64 felt socially excluded.
- Among men and women with severe disabilities, the figures were 14.6% and 16.9%, respectively.
- Employment rates increased between 2014 and 2023 regardless of disability status.
- Being employed was associated with a lower perception of social exclusion.
- The benefits of gainful employment were particularly evident among men with severe disabilities.

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ABSTRACT

Background: There is strong evidence that persons with disabilities are at greater risk of social exclusion in various areas of life. However, the role of employment for perceived social exclusion (PSE) among persons with disabilities has not yet been sufficiently researched.

Objective: This study addresses this gap by analyzing the mediating role of employment on the relationship between disabilities and PSE in women and men of later working age (40–64 yrs.).

Methods: We used a pooled data set from the 2014–2023 survey waves with 11,680 observations from the German Ageing Study (DEAS), a nationally representative longitudinal study of Germans over the age of 40. The Global Activity Limitation Indicator (GALI) was used as a measure of disability. PSE was measured with a scale developed by Bude and Lantermann covering four statements such as “I feel like I do not really belong to society”. We performed logistic regression analyses and counterfactual-based causal mediation analyses.

Results: For men with severe disabilities, employment accounted for almost half of the difference in PSE between individuals with and without severe disabilities. For women with severe disabilities, the effect of employment was less pronounced, accounting for 15.0% of the difference. While employment rates increased between 2014 and 2023 regardless of disability status, the employment-gap between persons with and without disabilities persisted.

Conclusions: The inclusion of individuals with disabilities into the labor market while promoting self-determined work remains an important social policy goal in Germany.

1. Introduction

The social model of disability (SMD) fundamentally changed the theorization of disability by shifting the analytical focus from the individual to the societal level and by emphasizing the difference between

the terms impairment and disability. While impairment is a medical condition, disability is the result of the interaction between persons with impairments and barriers in the physical, attitudinal and social environment. According to the SMD it is mainly these barriers that creates the disability, not the medical condition (Durell, 2014; Goering, 2015;

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Hogan, 2019). The model has been criticized for insufficient consideration of the role of the biological and psychological condition of persons with disabilities (Goering, 2015; Hughes, 2009). The current discourse emphasized that people benefit most when both the biological and social dimensions of disabilities are taken into account (Adam & Koutsoklenis, 2023; Anastasiou & Kauffman, 2013). Based on a biopsychosocial model, the International Classification of Functioning, Disabilities and Health (ICF) integrates both the medical and the social perspective. It enables a detailed description of the experiences of a person with a disability, including the barriers and facilitating factors in the environment that affect a person's functioning, such as physical accessibility of buildings or discrimination (Schneidert et al., 2003; WHO, 2001). The ICF also recognizes that functional status can limit a person's ability to participate in social activities, such as participating in working life (Martins, 2015).

Over the past decades, persons with disabilities have experienced significant improvements in terms of their economic, social and societal participation (Blanck & Adya, 2017; United Nations, 2016). However, though policy is striving towards the inclusion of persons with disabilities, they are still at higher risk of social exclusion (SE) in terms of education, income, employment, mobility and access to public and private services (Jones & McVicar, 2020). For example, Belzunegui-Eraso et al. found that persons with disabilities are at greater risk of SE and this relationship is accompanied by others variables, such as experiencing chronic illness or financial poverty (Belzunegui-Eraso et al., 2018). Discrimination against persons with disabilities (i.e. 'ableism') contributes to social exclusion and promotes feelings of being excluded from socially valued activities such as gainful employment. According to Huxhold et al. (Huxhold et al., 2022), people experience social exclusion when they do not see themselves as part of society, a perception that indicates a lack of social belonging. Existing research employs different assumptions about the relationship between SE and health impairments. While some authors consider SE as a cause of poor health, others regard SE as a consequence of poor health or as a mediator (van Bergen et al., 2018). Supporting a bidirectional relationship between health and SE, Sacker et al. found that poor health predicts SE as well as SE predicts poor health (Sacker et al., 2017). Using a measure of SE that address the feeling of being excluded from society, Kristensen et al. found an association between multimorbidity and perceived social exclusion (Kristensen et al., 2019). Moreover, Hajek and König found that feelings of social exclusion were associated with a higher risk of falls (Hajek & König, 2017).

Participation in paid (competitive) work is of crucial importance for social inclusion and quality of life as it contributes to people's participation in economic, cultural and social life (Bilevičienė et al., 2016). Several studies have demonstrated that the benefits of work also hold for persons with disabilities, indicating that employment can promote their quality of life, well-being and autonomy (Almalky, 2020; Robertson et al., 2019). With the ratification of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UN CRPD) in 2006 nearly 200 countries have committed to ensure equalized access to schooling, vocational education, training, and work (Nations U. Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), 2025). Germany is making various efforts to implement Article 27 of the UN CRPD. For example, employers with at least 20 jobs are required to fill at least 5% of their positions with persons with severe disabilities. Companies that do not meet this quota must pay a compensatory levy, which is used for inclusion measures (Lichter & Ehlert-Hoshmand, 2025). However, persons with disabilities are still among the most disadvantaged groups when it comes to social participation in the workforce. Compared to the general population, they have lower labor market participation, lower work intensity and a higher risk of in-work poverty (Eurofound, 2018). Recent studies confirm that the employment rate of persons with disabilities remains below that of persons without disabilities (50.8% compared with 75.0%) (Eurofound, 2021) while the proportion of those being unemployed and searching for a job, is twice as high (Lichter & Ehlert-Hoshmand,

2025). These findings point to the risk of persons with disabilities being stuck in long-term unemployment and struggling to access the labor market.

1.1. Aim of this study

While previous studies show that persons with disabilities are at greater risk of social exclusion in various areas of life, the role of employment on the association between disability and perceived social exclusion (PSE) remains underexplored. Particularly in the later stages of working life, when the proportion of persons with disabilities and those not in employment increases, the question arises as to what protective function paid work has for PSE of persons with disabilities. Against this backdrop, this study analyses the mediating role of employment on the relationship between disabilities and PSE among on women and men of later working age. In more detail, we address the following research questions:

1. What is the relationship between disability and PSE, and how has it developed between 2014 and 2023?
2. How has the paid (competitive) work of persons with and without disabilities developed over time?
3. Are persons with disabilities in paid work less affected by PSE than those who are not in paid work?
4. What influence does paid work have on the relationship between disability and PSE?

2. Methods

2.1. Data

We used data from the German Ageing Survey (DEAS), a nationally representative longitudinal study of Germans over the age of 40, which was launched by the German federal government in the mid-1990s. The primary goal of DEAS is to provide a representative national database containing information on the living conditions of the older population. To this end, a cohort-sequential design has been set up combining large cross-sectional samples with longitudinal samples. The cross-sectional samples (baseline samples) are drawn up every 6 years (beginning in 1996). Each baseline sample is followed over time, so that in addition to the cross-sectional sample also longitudinal data were collected. Due to the coronavirus pandemic, no new sample could be drawn in 2021. Instead, it was only possible to conduct a repeat survey of individuals who had already participated in previous survey waves, DEAS uses a two-stage sampling method. Out of the 12,000 municipalities in Germany, a random sample of 290 municipalities was initially drawn in 1996. The basic samples were stratified by gender, age and region. Individuals who participated in the baseline survey and gave their written consent were contacted for future assessments. Further information on the study design can be found in Klaus et al. (Klaus et al., 2017) For this study, we used a pooled dataset on 11,680 observations of women and men covering the 2014, 2017, 2021, and 2023 survey waves, for which information on PSE was available. These 11,680 observations are based on 5747 individuals who participated in the surveys an average of twice between 2014 and 2023 (minimum: 1, maximum: 4). We focused on persons of later working age because we assume that this group is particularly at risk of social exclusion, as both the proportion of persons with disabilities and the proportion of persons without employment is increasing. We have expanded the age group under study to include people aged 40 to 64 in order to increase the number of cases and thus the statistical power. The weighted sample characteristics stratified by disability status are displayed in Table 1. The proportion of missing values varied between 0 and 2.4%; they were excluded from the analysis.

Table 1
Weighted sample characteristics in % by disability status (n = 11,680).

	No limitations n = 7979 (68,3%)	Limited but not severely n = 2464 (21.1%)	Severely limited n = 1237 (10.6%)
Mean Age (SD)	53.0 (6.2)	54.1 (6.2)	54.9 (5.9)
Gender			
men	72.3	18.1	9.6
women	66.2	22.6	11.3
missing ¹	0.2	0.2	0.5
Educational level			
low	19.7	25.4	32.5
intermediate	36.6	39.5	36.6
high	43.7	35.1	30.9
Missing (n)	0.1	0	0.1
Household net income²			
< 80% median	22.1	32.1	38.8
80% - < 120%	31.4	29.7	32.8
≥ 120%	46.4	22.3	28.5
missing	2.4	2.4	2.3
Employed			
yes	86.9	73.7	54.5
no	13.1	26.3	45.5
missing	0.3	0.4	0.4
Family status			
married	72.9	66.1	65.4
separated / divorced	12.3	17.1	18.1
single	12.3	13.6	13.4
widowed	2.4	3.2	3.2
missing	0	0.1	0.5
Migration background			
no	91.6	92.0	92.8
yes, migrated myself	7.4	7.8	6.5
Yes, parents migrated	1.0	0.2	0.7
missing	0	0.1	0
Chronic diseases³			
0	55.4	21.5	16.0
1	30.9	34.6	23.4
2	10.1	22.8	28.3
3+	3.6	22.1	32.2
missing	0	0	0

Notes: numbers of observations, (Goering, 2015) the missing values in percentages are not added together with the valid values to 100%, but are added separately. ² based on modified equivalence scale, (Durell, 2014) = maximum number of observations, n= maximum number of observations.

2.2. Disability

We used the Global Activity Limitation Indicator (GALI) as a measure of disability. The single-question instrument defines disability based on self-reported limitations in usual activities due to a health problem for at least the past six months. Participants were asked to rate whether they are 'severely limited', 'limited but not severely', or 'not limited at all' in the activities they typically do because of a health issue. We have retained this distinction between the three categories in our analysis to reflect the fact that a disability is not a binary condition that is either present or absent. We are aware that reality is far more complex than this classification suggests. GALI is a concept widely used in surveys like the European Health Interview Survey (EHIS) or the EU statistics on income and living conditions (EU-SILC) to measure disability. The measure proved to have good and sufficient validity and reliability (van Oyen et al., 2006; Van Oyen et al., 2018).

2.3. Perceived social exclusion (PSE)

PSE was measured with a scale developed by Bude and Lantermann (2006) that consists of the four following items: "I'm worried to be left behind", 2. "I feel like I do not really belong to society, 3 "I feel that I'm left out and 4. I feel excluded from society. Each answer options ranging

from 1 to 4 (1 = "strongly agree" to 4 = "strongly disagree"). All responses were recoded so that high values reflect a high perceived level of social exclusion. (Böger et al., 2017) The scale represents the average of the item values of at least 50% of items. The threshold for indicating perceived social exclusion was set > 2.5 as individuals above this value rated statements indicating social exclusion as at least partially applicable. In order to psychometrically test this theoretically derived cut-off value, we performed sensitivity analyses with different cut-off values. A cut-off value of 3 was associated with too few cases (men / women: n = 67 / 86) and was therefore rejected. Compared to the selected threshold value of > 2.5, the threshold values of 1.5 and 2.0 showed a lower ability to distinguish the odds of social exclusion depending on the severity of the disability, as the results of logistic regression analyses showed. This suggests that the selected cut-off value is also reasonable from a psychometric point of view.

2.4. Employment status

All persons were defined as employed, regardless of whether they were employed or self-employed and also regardless of the extent of their employment. In the data set, 3.0% were mini-jobbers (up to 10 h per week), 25.3% were employed part-time (11 to 34 h), and 71.7% were employed full-time (35 h and more).

2.5. Confounders

For analyzing the temporal development of disability, PSE, and employment, we included age as a control variable and did not adjust for sociodemographic factors or health status, in order to take into account possible changes over time in these factors rather than controlling for them. For analysing the influence of employment on the association between disability and PSE, we controlled for age and the number of chronic diseases to adjust for severity of impairment because medical conditions could be a confounding variable that influences both employment and PSE. We used a categorical variable with the values 0, 1, 2, and 3 and more chronic diseases based on the following list of diseases: diabetes, heart attack, angina pectoris, heart failure, stroke, arthrosis, osteoporosis, inflammatory joint or spinal disease, chronic lung disease, cancer, gastric or duodenal ulcer, incontinence, parkinson's disease and glaucoma or macular degeneration. As persons with mental health conditions are particularly vulnerable to social exclusion (Boardman, 2011; Böger et al., 2017), we also controlled for mental illness (e.g., panic attacks, depression, psychosis). In addition, we controlled for the sociodemographic variables marital status (married, divorced, single, and widowed), migration background (no migration background, yes, self-migrant, and yes, parents immigrated), and educational level (low, medium, and high educational level) as potential confounding factors for the influence of employment on the relationship between disability and PSE.

2.6. Statistical analysis

Research questions 1 to 3 were calculated on the basis of logistic regression analyses, while causal mediation analyses were performed for research question 4 (see above).

We first analyzed the relationship between PSE (dependent variable) and disability status (independent variable) stratified by gender using clustered standard errors to account for the nested data structure resulting from the fact that in some cases there are multiple observations of the same person. We calculated odds ratios (OR) and predicted probabilities that estimate the adjusted prevalence rates of PSE. We then analyzed the temporal development of PSE between 2014 and 2023, using a categorical time-variable covering four time-points (2014, 2017, 2021 and 2023) with the first period being set to the reference category. In order to determine the predicted probabilities of PSE depending on disability status and survey year, we calculated the interaction term

“survey year*disability status” stratified by gender. Due to the small sample size of persons affected by PSE in the respective survey year, we could not differentiate according to the severity of disability.

Using the same technique, we examined how employment status developed over time depending on disability status and gender. We calculated separated models for the dependent variables ‘not in employment’, ‘part-time employment’ (up to 34 h per week) and ‘full-time employment’ (>34 h per week) (coded as 1=apply and 0=not apply) and again estimated odds ratios (OR) and predicted probabilities based on the interaction term “survey year*disability status. Moreover, we calculated the interaction term employment status*disability status to determine the relationship between disability status and employment status on PSE. For these analyses, in addition to age, we controlled for number of illnesses and mental condition to determine the significance of employment for perceived social exclusion, adjusted for medical conditions (see ‘confounders’ above).

Finally, we conducted counterfactual-based causal mediation analyses to examine the role of paid (competitive) work as a mediator on the relationship between disability and PSE. Traditional regression-based approaches to mediation analysis tend to produce biased estimates of direct and indirect effects, as they do not account for interactions between exposure and mediator and make strong assumptions about the absence of confounding factors. Causal mediation analysis under the potential-outcomes framework attempts to overcome these limitations by allowing for a decomposition of the total effect that takes into account non-linearities and exposure-mediator interactions (Rijnhart et al., 2021; Valente et al., 2020).

The framework of potential outcomes simultaneously considers two different effects of exposure, namely its effect on the outcome (outcome model Y) and its effect on the mediator (mediator model M). The combination of these effects leads to a total of four different hypothetical scenarios (Y1M1, Y0M0, Y1M0 and Y0M1) (Qin, 2024), which are presented in Table 2. For example, Y1M1 represents a scenario (PSE value) in which everyone is exposed (disabled) and experiences the mediator associated with being exposed. Accordingly, Y0M0 represents the PSE value of a scenario in which everyone is not exposed and experiences the mediator associated with being not exposed. In addition, there are two cross-world potential outcomes. For example, Y1M0 is the expected value of PSE when everyone has a disability but counterfactually experiences the value of the mediator associated with having no disability.

Table 2
Counterfactual framework of the mediation model.

Potential outcomes	Description
Y[1, M(1)] or in short Y1M1	Value of the outcome (PSE) when everyone is exposed (disability: yes) and experiences the mediator (employment) associated with being exposed
Y[0, M(0)] or in short Y0M0	Value of the outcome (PSE) when everyone is not exposed (disability: no) and experiences the mediator (employment) associated with being not exposed
Y[1, M(0)] or in short Y1M0	Value of the outcome (PSE) when everyone is exposed but counterfactually experiences the value of the mediator associated with being not exposed
Y[0, M(1)] or in short Y0M1	Value of the outcome (PSE) when everyone is not exposed but counterfactually experiences the value of the mediator associated with being exposed
Effects	
Total effect (TE) Y[1, M(1)] – Y[0, M(0)]	The average difference (effect) in PSE when everyone is exposed (disability: yes) versus when no one is exposed.
Direct effect (DE) Y[1, M(0)] – Y[0, M(0)]	The average direct effect of disability on the outcome when the mediator is held at its value associated with being not exposed
Indirect effect (IE) Y[1, M(1)] – Y[1, M(0)]	The average indirect effect through a mediator when the exposure is switched from ‘yes’ to ‘no’ in its effect on the mediator but keep the exposure fixed at value ‘yes’ in its effect on the outcome

Notes: PSE = Perceived social exclusion.

The total, direct and indirect effects can be calculated from these four potential outcomes (Table 2). The *total effect* estimates the differences in PSE that we would expect if everyone had a disability versus if no one has a disability (Y1M1 – Y0M0). The *indirect effect* estimates the average effect when “switching” the exposure from ‘disability’ to ‘no disability’ in its effect on the mediator but keep the exposure fixed at value of ‘disability’ in its effect on the outcome (Y1M1-Y1M0). Finally, the *direct effect* estimates the effect of disability on PSE when the mediator is held at its value associated with ‘no disability’ (Y1M0-Y0M0). While the causal mediation approach allows for exposure-mediator interactions, it relies on the same assumptions of the absence of unmeasured confounding for the association between exposure and outcome, and mediator and outcome, which are generally required for causal inference. To minimize bias due to confounding, we controlled for age, severity of illness, the presence of mental illness and sociodemographic variables (see ‘confounders’ above). However, given the non-experimental study design, it cannot be ruled out that other factors such as personality traits, attitudes toward work, or labor market conditions may be relevant confounding factors. Therefore, no causal relationships can be determined between disability and employment, or between employment and PSE. Taking this limitation into account, we use the terms indirect and direct effect to describe the results in the usual terminology of mediation analysis.

We used a logit model for our binary mediator (employment yes/ no) and binary outcome (PSE yes/ no) and calculated different models for moderate and severe disabilities separately for women and men. For all mediation analyses, we controlled for age (interval scaled), number of illnesses (categorical: 0,1,2, and 3 or more), and mental illness (yes / no). We stratified the data by gender to determine whether the significance of employment as a mediator differs between women and men. Moreover, population weights were employed to match the official population statistics. One exception was the subgroup-analysis of the temporal development of employment depending on disability status, where the unweighted results yielded more valid values in the time trend. All analyses were performed with STATA v18 (Stata Corp, 2015).

3. Results

Compared to men, women were more frequently (severely) limited in their daily activities (Table 1). It showed that social disadvantages in terms of school education, employment status and adjusted household net income increased with the severity of limitations. Furthermore, the severity of limitations increased with the number of chronic conditions.

3.1. Relationship between disability and PSE

As depicted in Fig. 1, 6.3% of men and 6.6% of women felt socially excluded from society. In both genders, PSE gradually increased with increasing severity of the limitations. Among men without limitations, the proportion of PSE was 4.0%, while among those with severe limitations it was 14.6%. Among women, the corresponding figures were 4.2% and 16.9%. Accordingly, women and men with moderate and, in particular, severe limitations had significantly higher odds of PSE compared to persons without limitations (Appendix Table 1).

3.2. Temporal development of the relationship between disability status and PSE

Between 2014 and 2023, PSE increased among men, while it decreased among women (Fig. 2). However, temporal changes for both genders mainly failed to reach statistical significance (Appendix Table 2).

Fig. 1. PSE by disability status.

Fig. 2. Development of PSE by disability status in women and men.

Fig. 3. Temporal development of employment status by disability status.

3.3. Temporal development of employment status of persons with and without disabilities

Men were more likely than women to be employed full-time, while women were significantly more likely to be employed part-time (Fig. 3). At each time point, men and women in particular with severe limitations were more frequently not employed. For example, in 2023, 9% of men and 13% of women without limitations were not employed whereas the respective figure of men and women with severe limitations were 37.1 and 40.5%. Over time, the proportion of non-employed women and men decreased for all disability status while the proportion of part-time and full-time employment increased (Fig. 3 and Appendix Table 3a und 3b).

3.4. Relationship between disability status and employment status on PSE

With a proportion of 4.1% and 3.7% respectively, PSE was lowest in working women and men without disabilities, while not employed women and men with severe disabilities were the most affected, with a share of 15.1% and 18.2% respectively (Appendix Fig. 1). Among men with severe disability who were in paid employment, PSE was significantly lower at 5.3% than among those who were not working (OR: 0.24, 95% CI: 0.09–0.68) (Appendix Table 4). Furthermore, men without limitations who were not employed were more affected by PSE than those who were severely limited but employed (11.1% versus 5.3%). Among women, there is a stronger correlation between employment and PSE in case of moderate limitations: only 4.6% of employed women, but 11.1% of unemployed women with moderate limitations were affected by PSE.

3.5. Causal mediation analysis: effect of employment on the relationship between disability and PSE

Analyses of potential outcomes for women revealed that the share of PSE is 7.8% in a scenario where every woman has a moderate limitation and experiences the employment status associated with having moderate limitations (Y1M1, Fig. 4, A1). In contrast, the share of PSE was reduced to 4.4% in a scenario where no women have moderate limitations and experiences the mediator associated with being not exposed (Y0M0, Fig. 4, A1). The total effect estimates the difference between these scenarios and gave a value of 3.4%-points. The indirect effect estimates a difference of 0.6%-points which means that 17.6% of the total

effect was mediated through employment. In women, the total effect size for severe limitations was higher compared to men (11.1%-points versus 8.0%-points). However, the indirect effect via the mediator was smaller here, i.e., 15.0% or 1.7%-points of the effect of severe limitations on PSE was mediated through employment (Fig. 4, A2). In contrast, in men almost the half of the effect of severe limitations on PSE (49.3%) was mediated through employment, i.e., 3.9%-points (IE) out of 8.0%-points (TE) (Fig. 4, B2). The opposite is true for moderate limitations, where the overall impact on PSE is higher for men than for women (6.9%-points vs. 3.4%-points). However, only 8.6% of the effect in men is mediated by employment (Fig. 4, B1).

4. Discussion

To our knowledge, this is the first study to quantify how much of the inequality in PSE between persons with and without disabilities of later working age are explained by participation in paid (competitive) work. Our main finding is that particularly men with severe disability who are engaged in paid work experience significant less social exclusion than those who are not employed.

4.1. PSE in persons with and without disabilities

In line with the study by Djouadi et al. (2021), PSE does not affect a large part of the population in our study, as was initially assumed by the authors of the concept (Bude & Lantermann, 2006). We found that in men and women of later working age, 6.3% and 6.6% respectively, feel socially excluded, that is, they are worried to be left behind and feel not really belong to society. Since we focused on the 40 to 64 age group, it could be that older persons are more affected by social exclusion in Germany. In line with this assumption, the study by Böger et al. (2017) shows that PSE tended to be higher among persons over 70, at 7%, but overall there were only minor differences between age groups. The EU social policy framework emphasizes that persons with disabilities are among the vulnerable group who are at risk of social exclusion (Tuparevska et al., 2020). In accordance with this, we found increased levels of PSE in individuals with disabilities compared to unaffected persons. Furthermore, it shows that PSE also varies within the group of persons with disabilities depending on the extent of disability. In persons with severe disabilities, PSE increased in men and women to 14.6% and 16.9%, respectively. While the overall proportion of PSE was quite

Fig. 4. Causal mediation analysis of the effect of employment on the relationship between moderate and severe disability and PSE.

similar between genders, different trends evolved over time. While the PSE tended to increase among men regardless of disability status, it generally declined among women. These gender specific pattern should be further investigated to validate this finding and to elaborate the drivers behind it.

4.2. The mediating role of employment on PSE

In alignment with previous research, we found that participants with disabilities had lower labor market participation and lower work intensity compared to participants without disabilities. Thus, while employment rates increased in our study between 2014 and 2023 for all persons of later working age regardless of disability status, the employment-gap between persons with and without disabilities persisted. According to the social role theory, paid work provides social status and economic independency and promotes personal fulfilment and well-being (Tuparevska et al., 2020). Previous studies have shown that the benefits of work also apply to persons with disabilities, suggesting that employment can promote their quality of life and well-being (Almalky, 2020; Robertson et al., 2019). For example, the study by Brouwers et al. (2024) found that paid employment provides many benefits for well-being of adults with autism such as ‘purpose,’ ‘social contacts,’ ‘growth and use of talents,’ and ‘income and freedom’. Our study adds that employment also has a positive impact on people’s sense of belonging to society. This finding is consistent with an EU study which found that a much smaller proportion of the working population feel excluded from society than the long-term unemployed or persons who are unable to work due to disability (Eurofound, 2018). In our study, particularly among men with severe limitations, being employed reduced the difference in PSE between persons with and without disabilities by almost half, i.e. by 49.3%. For women with severe disabilities, the effect of employment was less pronounced with a proportion of PSE mediated by employment of 15.0%. This gender difference might reflect different meanings of employment for women and men which may root in different role models in which men are primarily responsible for gainful employment and women are primarily responsible for family care. In line with this, the proportion of part-time employment in our study is significantly higher among women. It could be that the role of gainful employment is more central for men, and that not fulfilling this role is therefore associated with a stronger sense of exclusion among men than among women. Another possible explanation could be that the type or quality of employment differs between genders. The systematic review by Campos-Serna et al. (2013) shows that working women experience greater job insecurity, less control, poorer contractual working conditions, and lower professional status compared to men. These more adverse working conditions may have contributed to the fact that not being in employment is less significantly associated with feelings of social exclusion among women. Further research is needed to systematically investigate these possible explanations.

4.3. Practical implications

Most of the measures to tackle social exclusion from the labor market aimed at providing individuals with disabilities with relevant skills, competences and knowledge to make them “fit” for wage work. Such approaches have been criticized because they justify the exclusion of these persons from the labor market solely on the basis of their individual characteristics and capabilities (Grover & Piggott, 2015). In contrast, the social model of disability stresses that persons with disabilities are disadvantaged by socially embedded barriers, for instance disability-related prejudice, bureaucratic difficulties in accessing available services, barriers to entering vocational education and training, limited training resources for employers, and a lack of professional support (Blanck et al., 2025; Eurofound, 2021). Therefore, consideration should be given not only to the integration of persons with disabilities into the labor market, but also to adapting work to the needs of persons

with disabilities (Grover & Piggott, 2015). One concern raised by Brouwers et al. (2024), which could arise from the goal of greater participation of persons with disabilities in the labor market, is that this could lead to increased work pressure and be used to justify cuts in disability benefits. As Grint points out, work does not only provide positive effects, but can also have negative consequences if it is not self-determined and offers no opportunities for personal development (Grint, 2005). Efforts to increase the employment rate among persons with disabilities should therefore be free of pressure and sanctions and should promote personality-enhancing working conditions. While employment is revealed to be significant in reducing PSE of persons with disabilities, our study also shows that even in a scenario where the employment participation of persons with disabilities is equal to persons without disabilities, a substantial proportion of higher PSE remains. This points to the need to address also other sources of PSE in daily life, such as stigmatization or participation restrictions in daily social activities.

4.4. Limitations

Since we focused on persons with disabilities of advanced working age, our findings cannot be generalized to all individuals with disabilities of working age. Therefore, the importance of employment for younger persons with disabilities should be the subject of further studies. The DEAS data used does not distinguish between employment in the open labor market and employment in sheltered facilities such as workshops for persons with disabilities (WfbM). Therefore, respondents who work in WfbM cannot be identified separately and are classified as either employed or unemployed based on their own statements, which can lead to misclassifications. Further studies should specifically examine how work experience in WfbM affects PSE. Due to the coronavirus pandemic, it was not possible to draw a new sample in 2021. Instead, it was only possible to conduct a repeat survey of individuals who had already participated in previous survey waves, which could limit comparability between years. While the causal mediation approach allows for exposure-mediator interactions, it relies on the same assumptions of the absence of unmeasured confounding for the association between exposure and outcome, and mediator and outcome, which are generally required for causal inference. Hence, though we controlled for possible observed confounders, we cannot rule out that unobserved confounders may have biased the findings of our study.

5. Conclusions

We found that employment had a positive effect on PSE, which was most pronounced among men with severe disabilities. While employment rates increased between 2014 and 2023 for all persons of later working age independent of disability status, the employment-gap between persons with and without disabilities persisted. Promoting the inclusion of individuals with disabilities into the labor market without pressure or sanctions and while ensuring self-determined work therefore remains an important social policy goal in Germany.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies

No generative AI or AI-assisted technologies were used in the writing process for this article.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Stefanie Sperlich: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Julia Graßhoff:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Johannes Beller:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

Appendix

Appendix Table 1

Perceived social exclusion by disability status in women and men aged 40–64 yrs.

	OR	95% CI	
		lower	upper
Women			
Not limited	1		
Limited but not severe	2.00***	1.36	2.95
Severely limited	4.54***	2.94	6.99
Men			
Not limited	1		
Limited but not severe	3.00***	1.95	4.60
Severely limited	4.15***	2.54	6.77

Notes: Logistic regression of perceived social exclusion (mean value ≥ 2.6) on disability status (reference category: not limited), adjusted for age. OR = odds ratios, 95%CI = 95% confidence interval, *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001.

Appendix Table 2

Temporal development of perceived social exclusion by disability status in women and men aged 40–64 yrs.

	Not limited			(Severely) limited		
	OR	95% CI		OR	95% CI	
		lower	upper		lower	upper
Women						
2014	1			1		
2017	1.15	0.60	2.19	0.87	0.56	1.35
2021	0.65	0.34	1.27	0.52*	0.29	0.92
2023	0.66	0.36	1.18	0.67	0.33	1.33
Men						
2014	1			1		
2017	1.24	0.71	2.17	0.86	0.50	1.46
2021	1.07	0.39	2.93	1.22	0.53	2.80
2023	1.31	0.61	2.82	1.19	0.56	2.53

Notes: Logistic regression of perceived social exclusion (mean value ≥ 2.6) on time trend (reference category: 2014), stratified by disability status, adjusted for age. OR = odds ratios, 95%CI = 95% confidence interval, *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001.

Appendix Table 3a

Temporal development of employment status by disability status in men aged 40–64 yrs.

	(Severely) limited			Limited but not severely			Not limited		
	OR	95% CI		OR	95% CI		OR	95% CI	
		lower	upper		lower	upper		lower	upper
Non-Employment									
2014	1			1			1		
2017	0.43**	0.27	0.69	0.71*	0.51	0.99	0.65**	0.52	0.82
2021	0.90	0.52	1.55	0.74	0.52	1.06	0.49***	0.38	0.65
2023	0.58*	0.34	0.98	0.53*	0.33	0.84	0.35***	0.25	0.49
Part-Time Employment									
2014	1			1			1		
2017	1.27	0.47	3.50	1.09	0.43	2.74	1.50*	1.07	2.10
2021	1.19	0.33	4.37	3.30***	1.60	6.81	1.87***	1.27	2.74
2023	2.15	0.75	6.13	2.67*	1.20	5.96	1.34	0.85	2.10
Full-Time Employment									
2014	1			1			1		
2017	2.21***	1.41	3.48	1.42*	1.03	1.97	1.25*	1.02	1.53
2021	1.11	0.64	1.93	1.01	0.71	1.43	1.49**	1.18	1.88
2023	1.50	0.88	2.56	1.48	0.96	2.29	2.04***	1.53	2.71

Notes: Logistic regression of employment status (non employed, part-time and full-time) on time trend (reference category: 2014), stratified by disability status, adjusted for age. OR = odds ratios, 95%CI = 95% confidence interval, *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001.

Appendix Table 3b
Temporal development of employment status by disability status in **women** aged 40–64 yrs.

	(Severely) limited			Limited but not severely			Not limited		
	OR	95% CI		OR	95% CI		OR	95% CI	
		lower	upper		lower	upper		lower	upper
Non-Employment									
2014	1			1			1		
2017	0.88	0.60	1.30	0.67*	0.51	0.89	0.67***	0.57	0.80
2021	0.86	0.55	1.33	0.74	0.54	1.01	0.50***	0.41	0.62
2023	0.65	0.41	1.03	0.65*	0.46	0.91	0.35***	0.27	0.46
Part-Time Employment									
2014	1			1			1		
2017	1.30	0.83	2.04	1.06	0.79	1.42	1.20*	1.04	1.39
2021	1.37	0.82	2.30	1.32	0.96	1.83	1.38***	1.17	1.62
2023	1.30	0.77	2.19	1.18	0.84	1.65	1.38***	1.15	1.65
Full-Time Employment									
2014	1			1			1		
2017	0.92	0.59	1.44	1.44*	1.09	1.90	1.08	0.93	1.25
2021	0.97	0.57	1.63	1.09	0.79	1.50	1.18*	1.00	1.39
2023	1.30	0.79	2.14	1.33	0.96	1.84	1.23*	1.03	1.47

Notes: Logistic regression of perceived social exclusion (mean value ≥ 2.6) on time trend (reference category: 2014), stratified by disability status, adjusted for age. OR = odds ratios, 95%CI = 95% confidence interval, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Appendix Table 4
Relationship between disability status and employment status on perceived social exclusion.

	Women			Men		
	OR	95% CI		OR	95% CI	
	lower	upper	Lower	upper	upper	upper
Not employed / severe limitation	1			1		
Not employed / moderate limitation	0.69	0.36	1.31	0.77	0.37	1.62
Not employed / no limitation	0.54	0.27	1.07	0.55	0.23	1.32
Employed / severe limitation	0.57	0.27	1.22	0.24**	0.09	0.68
Employed / moderate limitation	0.26***	0.14	0.47	0.38**	0.19	0.75
Employed / no limitation	0.23***	0.12	0.44	0.17***	0.08	0.34

Notes: Logistic regression of perceived social exclusion (mean value ≥ 2.6) on interaction term disability status*employment status (reference category: not employed / severe limitation), adjusted for age, number of chronic complaints and mental illness. OR = odds ratios, 95%CI = 95% confidence interval, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Appendix Figure 1. PSE by disability status and employment status.

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